

Conference Abstract

The European weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in Hesse and Rhineland-Palatinate - occurrence, threats, protection measures

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Abstract

The European weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) is classified as "critically endangered" on the German Red List and occurs in Hesse and Rhineland-Palatinate, in the Upper Rhine Plain and the Wetterau region (Hesse). While populations are stable in the Wetterau region, strong fluctuations within populations can be observed in the Upper Rhine Plain. For this reason, a breeding and stocking program was carried out in 2014 to support and reintroduce the weatherfish in Hesse and Rhineland-Palatinate, as well as ecotoxicological studies on the sensitivity of the weatherfish's eggs and larval stages. This presentation (Suppl. material 1) will provide an overview of the occurrence of the weatherfish in Rhineland-Palatinate and Hesse, the success of the breeding and stocking program, and the threat factors to be considered, including ecotoxicological aspects.

Presenting author

Egbert Korte

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: The European weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in Hesse and Rhineland-Palatinate - occurrence, threats, protection measures [doi](#)

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